

Rethinking Education with ICT For Global Best Practices

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Abstract

The integration of information and communication technology (ICT) in education has the potential to revolutionize teaching and learning practices, as it enables access to a wider range of educational resources and promotes collaborative and personalized learning experiences. This is particularly important in today's globalized world, where technology is increasingly becoming a key driver of economic growth and social development. However, to fully realize the potential of ICT in education, it is important to adopt best practices that ensure access to technology for all students, provide ongoing teacher training, and promote responsible and safe digital citizenship. Rethinking education with information and communication technologies is necessary for global best practices in education. This is because technology has the potential to bridge the digital divide that exists between developed and developing countries, as well as between urban and rural areas within countries. By leveraging the power of ICT, we can help to ensure that all learners have access to high-quality education and the skills they need to succeed in the 21st century. In sum, the integration of information and communication technology in education represents a promising opportunity to improve teaching and learning practices and promote equitable access to education globally. However, adopting best practices and rethinking education with ICT is necessary to fully realize the potential of this transformative technology.

Keywords: Education, Global Best Practices, Information and Communications Technology

Introduction

Information and Communications Technology (ICT) is one of the wonderful gifts of modern science and technology which brought tremendous changes in library and information science. It seems to have opened up a new chapter in communication and facilitated global access to information crossing geographical limitations. ICT has a profound effect on the progress and development of human civilization. According to Singh (2021), ICT refers to the convergence of audiovisual and telephone networks with computer networks through a single link system. ICT means the use of computer-based technology and the internet to make information and communication services available to a wide range of users (Ward & Parr, 2010). ICT plays a vital role in the current and future development of society and the nation at large. Information and

communication technology is a diverse set of technological tools and resources used to communicate and to create, disseminate, store and manage information.

ICT can be used in education in many ways, including providing access to online learning resources, facilitating collaborative learning experiences, and enabling personalized learning experiences. Additionally, ICT can be used to support administrative functions, such as managing student records and communicating with parents and guardians. As technology continues to evolve, the use of ICT in education is likely to become even more important. Educators must stay up-to-date with the latest technologies and be prepared to integrate them into their teaching practices in order to provide students with the best possible learning experiences.

The field of education has undergone significant changes in recent years, particularly with the advent of information and communication technologies (ICTs). These technologies seem to have transformed the way we teach and learn, providing new opportunities for collaboration, engagement, and innovation. Information and Communication Technology (ICT) includes computers, the Internet, and electronic delivery systems such as radios, televisions, and projectors among others, and is widely used in today's education. Kent and Facer (2004) indicated that school is an important environment in which students participate in a wide range of computer activities, while the home serves as a complementary site for regular engagement in a narrower set of computer activities. Increasingly, ICT is being applied successfully in instruction, learning, and assessment. It is considered a powerful tool for educational change and reform. A number of previous studies have shown that the appropriate use of ICT can raise educational quality and connect learning to real-life situations (Lowther, et al. 2008; Weert & Tatnall, 2005).

All around us people are learning with the aid of new technologies: children are playing complex video games, workers are interacting with simulations that put them in challenging situations, students are taking courses at online schools and colleges, and adults are consulting Wikipedia. These technologies create learning opportunities that challenge traditional schools and colleges. These new learning niches enable people of all ages to pursue learning on their own terms. People around the world are taking their education out of school into homes, libraries, Internet cafes, and workplaces, where they can decide what they want to learn, when they want to learn, and how they want to learn. Who will benefit ultimately from this revolution?

According to a report by the World Bank (2016), ICTs can improve access to education, enhance the quality of teaching and learning, and support the development of critical thinking and problem-solving skills. However, the adoption of ICTs in education has been uneven, many schools and communities seems to be lacking the necessary infrastructure and training to fully utilize these technologies. In order to achieve global best practices in education, it is necessary to rethink how we integrate ICTs into the educational process.

To address this issue, this paper seeks to identify best practices in the use of ICTs in education and to promote their adoption on a global scale. This involves identifying the key challenges and barriers to adoption, as well as the policies and strategies that have been successful in promoting the use of ICTs in education. The paper also aims to identify the ethical and social implications of the use of ICTs in education and to explore ways to address these issues.

Global Best Practices in the Use of ICTs in Education

The use of ICT (Information and Communication Technology) in education has become increasingly popular in recent years, as it can enhance teaching and learning processes, improve access to educational resources, and facilitate communication between teachers and students. Here are some global best practices in the use of ICT in education:

1. **Develop a clear ICT policy:** A clear ICT policy can help guide decision-making around the use of technology in education. This might include guidelines for selecting technology, expectations for teacher training and support, and strategies for monitoring and evaluating effectiveness (United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO), 2011).
2. **Provide access to technology and connectivity:** Ensuring that all students have access to technology and connectivity is critical for promoting equitable access to education (UNESCO, 2017). This might involve providing devices like laptops or tablets, as well as ensuring that students have access to reliable internet connectivity.
3. **Integrate technology into the curriculum:** Technology should be integrated into the curriculum in a way that supports specific learning objectives and enhances traditional teaching methods (UNESCO, 2011). This might involve using technology to create interactive learning materials, facilitate collaborative learning, or provide personalized learning opportunities.
4. **Foster collaboration and sharing of best practices:** Collaboration and sharing of best practices is critical for promoting the effective use of technology in education (UNESCO, 2011). This might involve creating professional learning communities for teachers or providing opportunities for teachers to share resources and strategies.
5. **Monitor and evaluate effectiveness:** It is important to monitor and evaluate the effectiveness of technology integration in order to make informed decisions about future use (UNESCO, 2011). This might involve collecting data on student outcomes, conducting surveys of teachers and students, or engaging in ongoing formative assessment.
6. **Curriculum and Pedagogy:** The curriculum and pedagogy should be designed to promote critical thinking, problem-solving, creativity, and collaboration (Lai & Law, 2018). Teachers should be trained to use a range of teaching strategies and technologies to engage students (OECD, 2019). The curriculum should be relevant to the needs of students and should reflect the changing needs of the job market (World Economic Forum, 2018).
7. **Assessment and Feedback:** Assessment should be used to support student learning rather than just measuring performance (Black & Wiliam, 1998). Teachers should use a range

of assessment strategies to evaluate students' progress and provide timely feedback (Hattie & Timperley, 2007). Assessment should be aligned with the learning objectives and should be used to identify areas where students need additional support (Sadler, 1989).

8. **Teacher Training and Professional Development:** Teachers should receive ongoing training and professional development to stay up-to-date with the latest teaching strategies and technologies (Darling-Hammond et al., 2017). They should be encouraged to collaborate with their peers and share best practices (OECD, 2019). Professional development should be tailored to the individual needs of teachers and should be aligned with the school's goals and objectives (Guskey, 2002).
9. **Technology and Infrastructure:** Schools should have access to the necessary technology and infrastructure to support teaching and learning (Bebell & Kay, 2010). This includes access to computers, internet connectivity, and software applications. The technology should be reliable, easy to use, and should support collaboration and communication among students and teachers (British Educational Communications and Technology Agency (BECTA), 2003).
10. **Parental Involvement:** Parents should be encouraged to be actively involved in their child's education (Epstein, 1995). They should be provided with regular updates on their child's progress and should be given opportunities to participate in school activities. Schools should work with parents to create a supportive learning environment at home (Desforges & Abouchar, 2003).
11. **Inclusive Education:** Schools should be inclusive and cater to the diverse needs of students (UNESCO, 2017). This includes students with disabilities, students from different cultural backgrounds, and students with different learning needs. Teachers should be trained to use a range of teaching strategies to support all students and should be sensitive to their cultural and linguistic diversity (Gay, 2010).

Challenges and Barriers to Adoption of ICT in Education

1. **Infrastructure and Access:** One of the main challenges to the adoption of ICTs in education is the lack of infrastructure and access to technology. Many schools and communities in developing countries lack the necessary infrastructure to support the use of ICTs in education, such as reliable electricity, internet connectivity, and computers (Bebell & Kay, 2010). For example, in sub-Saharan Africa, only 10% of primary schools have internet access (UNESCO, 2019).
2. **Digital Divide:** The digital divide refers to the gap between those who have access to technology and those who do not. This divide can be geographic, economic, or cultural, and it can impact the ability of students to access and benefit from ICTs in education (Warschauer & Matuchniak, 2010). For instance, in the United States, students from low-income families are less likely to have access to computers and the internet at home, which can limit their ability to use ICTs for learning (Pew Research Center, 2018).
3. **Teacher Training and Professional Development:** Another challenge to the adoption of ICTs in education is the lack of teacher training and professional development. Many teachers may

not be familiar with the latest technologies or may not know how to integrate them into their teaching practices (Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD), 2019). In a study of teachers in 22 countries, 71% reported that they had not received any training on how to use ICTs for teaching (Eurydice, 2019).

4. **Cost:** The cost of implementing ICTs in education can be a significant barrier, especially in developing countries. The cost of purchasing and maintaining technology, as well as providing training and support, can be prohibitive for many schools and communities (Bebell & Kay, 2010). For example, in sub-Saharan Africa, the cost of internet access can be up to 30 times higher than in other regions (International Telecommunication Union (ITU), 2019).
5. **Pedagogical Approach:** The adoption of ICTs in education also requires a shift in pedagogical approach, from a teacher-centered to a learner-centered approach. This can be challenging for teachers who are used to traditional teaching methods (Lai & Law, 2018). In a survey of teachers in the United States, 57% reported that they were not comfortable with student-centered teaching (Project Tomorrow, 2018).
6. **Ethical and Social Implications:** There are also ethical and social implications to consider when adopting ICTs in education, such as data privacy and security, algorithmic bias, and the impact of automation on the workforce. These issues must be addressed to ensure that the use of ICTs in education is responsible and ethical (World Economic Forum, 2018). For example, in a study of ed-tech products, researchers found that many products failed to protect student data (Common Sense, 2018).

Policies and Strategies in Promoting Use of ICT in Education

Promoting the use of ICT in education requires policies and strategies that address a range of issues, including infrastructure, teacher training and support, curriculum development, and funding. Here are some policies and strategies that can help promote the use of ICT in education:

1. **Develop a national ICT in education policy:** A national policy can provide a framework for promoting the use of ICT in education, and can help guide decision-making around investments in technology. The policy should be developed in consultation with key stakeholders, including educators, policymakers, and technology experts.
2. **Provide infrastructure and connectivity:** Access to technology and connectivity is critical for promoting the use of ICT in education. Governments can invest in infrastructure, such as broadband networks and computer labs, to ensure that schools have the necessary resources to support technology integration.
3. **Develop teacher training programs:** Teachers need training to effectively integrate technology into their teaching practices. Governments can develop training programs, such as workshops and online courses, to help teachers develop the necessary skills and knowledge.
4. **Support curriculum development:** Curriculum development should be aligned with the use of ICT to ensure that technology is being used in a way that supports learning objectives. Governments can provide resources to support the development of digital learning materials and the integration of technology into existing curriculum.

5. **Provide funding for technology:** Funding is needed to purchase technology and provide ongoing support and maintenance. Governments can provide funding for schools to purchase technology, as well as for ongoing support and maintenance.
6. **Encourage public-private partnerships:** Public-private partnerships can provide additional resources and expertise to support the use of ICT in education. Governments can work with private sector partners to develop and implement technology initiatives, such as mobile learning programs or online learning platforms.

Ethical and social implications of the Use of ICTs in Education

The use of information and communication technologies (ICTs) in education has several ethical and social implications that need to be addressed to ensure that they are used responsibly and ethically. These include:

1. **Data Privacy and Security:** The use of ICTs in education raises important concerns about data privacy and security. Student data, such as grades and personal information, is often stored on digital systems, and there is a risk of this data being hacked or misused. Schools and educators need to ensure that they have appropriate security measures in place to protect student data (World Economic Forum, 2018).
2. **Algorithmic Bias:** The use of ICTs can also lead to algorithmic bias, which occurs when algorithms produce biased or discriminatory results. For example, an algorithm used to assess student achievement may be biased against certain groups of students. Educators need to be aware of the potential for algorithmic bias and take steps to address it (Baker & Siemens, 2014).
3. **Digital Divide:** The digital divide refers to the gap between those who have access to technology and those who do not. The use of ICTs in education can exacerbate this divide, as students who do not have access to technology may be at a disadvantage. Schools and educators need to work to bridge the digital divide and ensure that all students have access to the necessary technology (Bebell & Kay, 2010).
4. **Online Behaviour:** The use of ICTs can also raise important ethical and social considerations around online behavior. Students need to be taught how to behave responsibly online, including how to avoid cyberbullying and how to respect others' privacy and intellectual property rights. Educators need to ensure that students understand the ethical and social implications of their online behavior (International Society for Technology in Education, 2017).
5. **Changing Nature of Work:** The use of ICTs in education also has implications for the changing nature of work. As automation and artificial intelligence become more prevalent, students need to be prepared for a workforce that requires different skills than in the past.

Educators need to ensure that students are equipped with the necessary digital and soft skills to succeed in the future workforce (World Economic Forum, 2018).

Conclusion

The integration of information and communication technology (ICT) in education has become an increasingly important aspect of modern teaching and learning practices. The use of ICT can enhance learning, personalize instruction, and promote collaboration and communication among students. However, for ICT to be effective in education, it is important to ensure access to technology for all students, provide ongoing teacher training, and promote responsible and safe digital citizenship. By following best practices in the use of ICT in education, we can help to create a more equitable and effective education system for all learners, regardless of their geographic location or socioeconomic background. As such, rethinking education with information and communication technologies is necessary for global best practices in education.

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